

Humanlike manual activities in *Australopithecus*

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ABSTRACT

The evolution of the human hand is a topic of great interest in paleoanthropology. As the hand can be involved in a vast array of activities, knowledge regarding how it was used by early hominins can yield crucial information on the factors driving biocultural evolution. Previous research on early hominin hands focused on the overall bone shape. However, while such approaches can inform on mechanical abilities and the evolved efficiency of manipulation, they cannot be used as a definite proxy for individual habitual activity. Accordingly, it is crucial to examine bone structures more responsive to lifetime biomechanical loading, such as muscle attachment sites or internal bone architecture. In this study, we investigate the manual enthesal patterns of *Australopithecus afarensis*, *Australopithecus africanus*, and *Australopithecus sediba* through the application of the validated entheses-based reconstruction of activity method. Using a comparative sample of later *Homo* and three great ape genera, we analyze the muscle attachment site proportions on the thumb, fifth ray, and third intermediate phalanx to gain insight into the habitual hand use of *Australopithecus*. We use a novel statistical procedure to account for the effects of interspecies variation in overall size and ray proportions. Our results highlight the importance of certain muscles of the first and fifth digits for humanlike hand use. In humans, these muscles are required for variable in-hand manipulation and are activated during stone-tool production. The entheses of *A. sediba* suggest muscle activation patterns consistent with a similar suite of habitual manual activities as in later *Homo*. In contrast, *A. africanus* and *A. afarensis* display a mosaic enthesal pattern that combines indications of both humanlike and apelike manipulation. Overall, these findings provide new evidence that some australopith species were already habitually engaging in humanlike manipulation, even if their manual dexterity was likely not as high as in later *Homo*.

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1. Introduction

Hominin hand use is frequently addressed in human evolutionary studies. Investigating how it developed throughout the human lineage can provide insight into when and how hominins ceased to use their hands regularly for arboreal locomotion, the emergence of humanlike grasping techniques, or the onset of systematic tool production and use. As the fossil record is sparse and

the information to be gained from individual specimens is limited, early hominin hand use is deduced from comparisons with their closest living relatives.

The modern human hand is dexterous and typically used only for manipulation in Western societies. Its morphology and function are widely investigated in clinical and evolutionary contexts (e.g., Taylor and Schwarz, 1955; Jones and Lederman, 2006; Feix et al., 2016; Baksa et al., 2018). Humans are capable of various manipulatory tasks and different grasping techniques, among which power and precision grips have received particular attention in the literature (Napier, 1956; Landsmeer, 1962; Long II et al., 1970; Marzke et al., 1992; Maier and Hepp-Reymond, 1995; Marzke, 1997; Feix et al., 2016). In contrast, the hand of non-human primates is used for both locomotion (Susman and Stern, 1979; Matarazzo, 2008;

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Schmitt et al., 2016; Neufuss et al., 2017; Larson, 2018; Thompson, 2020; Leijnse et al., 2021) and manipulation (Christel, 1993; Byrne et al., 2001; Corp and Byrne, 2002; Marzke et al., 2015; Fragaszy and Crast, 2016; Bardo et al., 2017; Neufuss et al., 2019). Their manipulatory capabilities differ notably from those of humans, which can be partially attributed to differences in their bone shape (Kivell, 2016a; Orr, 2016) and muscular configuration (Lemelin and Diogo, 2016). In contrast to humans, little is known about muscle activities and coordination during manipulation in nonhuman primates (Bardo et al., 2017). The extent to which the primate hand is used for manipulatory tasks and the complexity of the applied techniques vary not only among primate species (e.g., see Christel, 1993; Bardo et al., 2017) but also among different communities (Krützen et al., 2011; Robbins et al., 2016; Kühl et al., 2019; Kalan et al., 2020). For example, some western chimpanzee groups, such as the Taï chimpanzees, habitually engage in pounding activities to crack nuts (Boesch-Achermann and Boesch, 1993; Visalberghi et al., 2015), whereas others do not (McGrew et al., 1997; Harmand and Arroyo, 2023). Similar behavior has been observed in long-tailed macaques (Gumert and Malaivijitnond, 2013) and bearded capuchin monkeys (Falótico et al., 2018; also see Harmand and Arroyo, 2023 for an extensive review on pounding behaviors in primates) who even unintentionally produce sharp-edged flakes during these activities (Proffitt et al., 2016, 2023).

Our knowledge about hand use in hominins is even more limited. The lack of soft-tissue preservation complicates the reconstruction of manual abilities and activities. Despite this limitation, it is of great interest to gain information on the capability and dexterity of hominin hands and the tasks they habitually performed. Apart from a general insight into an individual's habitual manual activities, investigating hand use in early hominins sheds light on important questions regarding biological and cultural coevolution.

Research on early hominin hand bones often focuses on their capability to produce and use stone tools. The earliest evidence of stone-tool production and use from the archaeological record is scarce and debated (Domínguez-Rodrigo et al., 2012; Harmand et al., 2015; Domínguez-Rodrigo and Alcalá, 2016; Archer et al., 2020) and does not necessarily shed light on the question of who made or used the tools. Therefore, analyzing the manual activity patterns of hominins dating to around the first archaeological evidence of tool-related behavior, such as members of the genus *Australopithecus*, can help elucidate the emergence of systematic stone tool use.

Previous research on australopith hand use frequently focused on the hand skeleton's external morphology (Marzke, 1983; Marzke and Shackley, 1986; Ricklan, 1987; Richmond et al., 2016; Kivell et al., 2018), including the examination of manual proportions (Alba et al., 2003; Green and Gordon, 2008; Rolian and Gordon, 2013; Almécija and Alba, 2014) and gross bone-shape analyses (Almécija et al., 2010; Marzke et al., 2010; Marchi et al., 2017; Galletta et al., 2019; Bowland et al., 2021; Kunze et al., 2022; Morley et al., 2022; Bardo et al., 2024; see also Kivell et al., 2023 for an extensive overview). Other approaches include the analysis of trabecular structures (Skinner et al., 2015; Dunmore et al., 2020a; Bird et al., 2024), investigations of cortical bone distribution (Dunmore et al., 2020a; Syeda et al., 2021), and biomechanical muscle modeling (Domalain et al., 2017; Karakostis et al., 2021a).

Analyzing the external morphology of bone can yield information on an individual's mechanical limitations or biomechanical efficiency, but most of its overall form (size and shape) is primarily genetically regulated and does not necessarily reflect lifetime habitual activity (Parfitt et al., 2000; Currey, 2002; Kivell, 2016b; Wallace et al., 2020). Nevertheless, specific aspects of bone

morphology, such as trabecular bone (Biewener et al., 1996; Ruff et al., 2006; Scherf et al., 2013, 2016; Tsegai et al., 2013; Kivell, 2016b; Stephens et al., 2018; Dunmore et al., 2024) or muscle attachment sites (Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016; Karakostis et al., 2017, 2019a, 2019b; Castro et al., 2022) are reportedly more heavily impacted by loading history and habitual activity. These structures respond to strain induced by mechanical loading through bone modeling and remodeling during life (Ruff et al., 2006). For example, as the interface of soft and hard tissue, muscle attachment sites experience strain caused by direct muscle loading and an osteogenic response (Benjamin et al., 2002; Schlecht, 2012; Cashmore and Zakrzewski, 2013; Foster et al., 2014). Consequently, frequent muscle use has been linked with a relative increase in enthesal area (Deymier-Black et al., 2015; Deymier et al., 2019; Karakostis et al., 2019a, 2019b; Schlecht et al., 2019; Castro et al., 2022; Turcotte et al., 2022; Karakostis and Wallace, 2023).

Muscle attachment sites, or entheses, have been used for activity reconstruction since the 1980s (e.g., Kennedy, 1983; Dutour, 1986; also see Jurmain et al., 2012). The approach is based on the assessment of changes in enthesal morphology caused by mechanical loading (Hawkey and Merbs, 1995; Benjamin et al., 2002; Schlecht, 2012). Over the years, the reliability of this approach has been hotly debated. Researchers have questioned the influence of intrinsic and extrinsic factors (age, sex, body height, nutrition, etc.) on attachment site morphology (e.g., see Rauch, 2005; Milella et al., 2012; Schlecht, 2012; Foster et al., 2014; Turcotte et al., 2022) and emphasized the shortcomings of scoring systems, a method commonly used to analyze enthesal change (Cashmore and Zakrzewski, 2013; Noldner and Edgar, 2013; Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016; Wilczak et al., 2017). The most frequently raised criticism is based on experimental studies that found no correlation between enthesal change and habitual activity (Zumwalt, 2006; Rabey et al., 2015; Williams-Hatala et al., 2016; Wallace et al., 2017; Turcotte et al., 2020). However, these studies present some methodological limitations (e.g., lack of multivariate approaches and issues with experimental design, see Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016; Karakostis et al., 2018a; Karakostis and Harvati, 2021; Karakostis, 2023 for a more detailed discussion). Furthermore, several recent experimental studies have supported a link between enthesal morphology and habitual activity (Deymier-Black et al., 2015; Deymier et al., 2019; Karakostis et al., 2019a, 2019b; Schlecht et al., 2019; Castro et al., 2021; Turcotte et al., 2022; Karakostis and Wallace, 2023).

The validated entheses-based reconstruction of activity method (VERA; Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016; Karakostis and Harvati, 2021; Karakostis, 2023) uses a multivariate approach to investigate the proportions among entheses and relies on them to identify patterns of habitual muscle activation. The method has been validated in both experimental studies (Karakostis et al., 2019a, 2019b; Castro et al., 2022; Karakostis and Wallace, 2023) and using a historical human skeletal sample of which substantial information is recorded, including, among others, age at death, sex, medical profile, and detailed occupational activities (Karakostis et al., 2017; Karakostis and Hotz, 2024). Focusing on enthesal proportions within individuals instead of comparing single entheses among individuals can account for influential factors affecting interindividual variability (Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016; Karakostis et al., 2018a). The validated entheses-based reconstruction of activity method has been previously applied to different populations of modern humans (Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016; Karakostis et al., 2017, 2020, 2021b; Bousquié et al., 2022; Karakostis and Hotz, 2024), Neanderthals (Karakostis et al., 2018a), and early fossil hominins (Kunze et al., 2022). The first application of this method to the manual behaviors of early hominins investigated enthesal

patterns on the first metacarpal (Kunze et al., 2022). We found that later *Homo* and nonhuman great apes differed in proportions of the first dorsal interosseus (DI1) attachment site, with the former presenting DI1 entheses that are proportionally larger than the other muscles attached to the first metacarpal. Electromyographic research has shown that this muscle is frequently activated during tool production and use (Marzke et al., 1998; Key et al., 2020). A proportionally large DI1 enthesis was also observed in most early hominins, including *Australopithecus sediba* and *Australopithecus afarensis*, but not in *Australopithecus africanus*, who presented an enthesal pattern more similar to gorillas (Kunze et al., 2022). In that study, we proposed that, despite their more primitive bone shape and comparatively low manual dexterity, *A. sediba* and *A. afarensis* likely habitually engaged in humanlike hand use, potentially including humanlike tool production and use (for which these species would have been anatomically capable; see Marzke, 1983).

Although the muscles attaching to the first metacarpal, specifically the opponens pollicis (OP) and DI1, play important roles in manipulation (Marzke, 1997; Marzke et al., 1998; Feix et al., 2015; Karakostis et al., 2021a), they represent only a small number of muscles involved in manipulative activities. Therefore, here we aim to investigate the habitual hand use in *A. sediba*, *A. afarensis*, and *A. africanus* by extending the analysis of enthesal patterns to additional entheses of the hand skeleton. We examine attachment sites on the metacarpals and proximal phalanges of the first and fifth ray and the third intermediate phalanx in a comparative framework, including later *Homo* and nonhuman apes (hereafter great apes). Previous work has highlighted the importance of the fifth ray for humanlike manipulation, including tool-related behaviors and power grasping (Marzke et al., 1998; Karakostis et al., 2017; Key et al., 2019; but see Syeda et al., 2023).

We expect later *Homo* and great apes to be distinct in their enthesal patterns. Based on our previous work (Kunze et al., 2022), we expect later *Homo* to show proportionally large DI1 attachment sites, as well as relatively large entheses of the fifth ray compared to the other muscles in the analysis. The fifth finger is essential for stabilization, in-hand manipulation, and power grasping, while also

being reportedly involved in tool production and use (Long et al., 1970; Marzke and Shackley, 1986; Marzke et al., 1998; Marzke, 2013; Key et al., 2019, 2020). In contrast, great apes will likely present proportionally larger entheses of the extrinsic finger flexors (e.g., the flexor digitorum superficialis [FDS] of the third intermediate phalanx) due to the central role finger flexion plays in arboreal locomotion (Susman and Stern, 1979; Syeda et al., 2023, 2024). Additionally, we expect them to display relatively larger attachment sites of the muscles related to thumb adduction as great apes are known to adduct their thumb frequently during manipulation (Christel, 1993; Dunmore et al., 2020b; Bardo et al., 2024). Finally, if our previous results on the attachment sites of the first metacarpal (Kunze et al., 2022) are representative of the entire hand skeleton, we would assume that *A. sediba* and *A. afarensis* show enthesal patterns similar to later *Homo*, whereas *A. africanus* would have more apelike enthesal proportions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

We used a comparative sample consisting of later *Homo* (Table 1), including recent ($n = 11$) and fossil *Homo sapiens* (Arene Candide 2, Ohalo 2, Qafzeh 9) and *Homo neanderthalensis* (Kebara 2, La Ferrassie 1, Shanidar 4), as well as *Gorilla gorilla* ($n = 7$), *Pan troglodytes* ($n = 8$), *Pongo abelii* ($n = 1$), and *Pongo pygmaeus* ($n = 3$; Table 2). Our early hominin specimens (Table 3) include an associated hand skeleton of *A. sediba* ($n = 1$; Malapa Hominin 2) and composite hand skeletons (pooling isolated bones) of *A. afarensis* ($n = 1$; A.L. 333/333w locality) and *A. africanus* ($n = 1$; Sterkfontein Member 4). The sample of recent *H. sapiens* includes identified individuals from the 19th century collection ‘Basel-Spitalfriedhof’ from Basel, Switzerland ($n = 3$) and the medieval collection from Grevenmacher, Luxemburg ($n = 8$). The nonhuman great ape sample stems from several localities (Table 2) and contains wild-caught and captive animals.

The attachment sites investigated in this study (Fig. 1) are mainly located on the bones of the thumb and the fifth ray. The only

Table 1
Details on later *Homo* sample.

ID	Species	Age	Sex	Date	Location	Institution	References
Arene Candide 2	Fossil <i>Homo sapiens</i>	~25	Male	12–11 ka	Italy	Museo Archeologico Del Finale, IT	Sparacello et al. (2018)
Ohalo 2	Fossil <i>Homo sapiens</i>	~35–40	Male	ca. 19 ka	Israel	Tel Aviv University, IL	Hershkovitz et al. (1995)
Qafzeh 9	Fossil <i>Homo sapiens</i>	15–19	Female	100–90 ka	Israel	Tel Aviv University, IL	Valladas et al. (1988)
Kebara 2	<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i>	25–30	Male	64–60 ka	Israel	Tel Aviv University, IL	Schwarz et al. (1989)
La Ferrassie 1	<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i>	Adult	Male	~45–43 ka	France	National Museum of Natural History in Paris, FR	Guérin et al. (2015)
Shanidar 4	<i>Homo neanderthalensis</i>	30–45	Male	100–60 ka	Iraq	Tel Aviv University, IL	Trinkaus (1983)
STJ-0137	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	31	Male	19th century AD	Basel, Switzerland	Natural History Museum of Basel, CH	Hotz and Steinke (2012)
STJ-0211	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	29	Male	19th century AD	Basel, Switzerland	Natural History Museum of Basel, CH	Hotz and Steinke (2012)
STJ-0264	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	41	Male	19th century AD	Basel, Switzerland	Natural History Museum of Basel, CH	Hotz and Steinke (2012)
GV 5	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	35–45	Male	13th–15th century AD	Grevenmacher, Luxembourg	University of Tübingen, DE	Trautmann (2012)
GV 12	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	30–40	Female	13th–15th century AD	Grevenmacher, Luxembourg	University of Tübingen, DE	Trautmann (2012)
GV 93	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	20–25	Female	13th–15th century AD	Grevenmacher, Luxembourg	University of Tübingen, DE	Trautmann (2012)
GV 105	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	30–40	Female	13th–15th century AD	Grevenmacher, Luxembourg	University of Tübingen, DE	Trautmann (2012)
GV 112	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	30–40	Male	13th–15th century AD	Grevenmacher, Luxembourg	University of Tübingen, DE	Trautmann (2012)
GV 117	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	20–25	Male	13th–15th century AD	Grevenmacher, Luxembourg	University of Tübingen, DE	Trautmann (2012)
GV 121	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	20–25	Female	13th–15th century AD	Grevenmacher, Luxembourg	University of Tübingen, DE	Trautmann (2012)
GV 132	Modern <i>Homo sapiens</i>	40–50	Male	13th–15th century AD	Grevenmacher, Luxembourg	University of Tübingen, DE	Trautmann (2012)

Abbreviations: CH = Switzerland; DE = Germany; FR = France; ID = identification number; IL = Israel; IT = Italy. References are provided for the dating of the fossil or the respective site.

Table 2
Details on great ape sample.

ID	Species	Age ^a	Sex	Wild-caught/captive	Provenance	Institution
1784	<i>Gorilla gorilla</i>	Adult	Female	Wild-caught	Gabon	State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart, DE
6294	<i>Gorilla gorilla</i>	Adult	Male	Wild-caught	Gabon	Natural History Museum Basel, CH
7464	<i>Gorilla gorilla</i>	Subadult	Male	Wild-caught	Gabon	State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart, DE
38230	<i>Gorilla gorilla</i>	Adult	Female	Captive	Wilhelma Zoo, Stuttgart, DE	State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart, DE
1353	<i>Gorilla gorilla</i>	Adult	Male	Captive	Fukuoka City Zoo, JP	Kobe Oji Zoo, JP ^b
167340	<i>Gorilla gorilla</i>	Adult	Female	Wild-caught	Cameroon	American Museum of Natural History, the US ^c
235603	<i>Gorilla gorilla</i>	Adult	Male	Captive	Bronz Zoo, US	American Museum of Natural History, the US ^c
1794	<i>Pan troglodytes</i>	Adult	Male	Wild-caught	Gabon	State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart, DE
2738	<i>Pan troglodytes</i>	Adult	Unknown	Wild-caught	Southern Cameroon	State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart, DE
10824	<i>Pan troglodytes</i>	Adult	Female	Captive	Zoological garden Basel, CH	Natural History Museum Basel, CH
51376	<i>Pan troglodytes</i>	Adult	Female	Wild-caught	DRC	American Museum of Natural History, US ^c
587	<i>Pan troglodytes</i>	Adult	Female	Captive	Kamine Zoo, JP	PRI Kyoto University, JP ^b
498	<i>Pan troglodytes</i>	Adult	Female	Captive	Tennoji Zoo, JP	Tobe Zoological Park, JP ^b
51205	<i>Pan troglodytes</i>	Adult	Unknown	Wild-caught	Zaire	American Museum of Natural History, US ^c
89355	<i>Pan troglodytes</i>	Adult	Male	Wild-caught	Ivory Coast	American Museum of Natural History, US ^c
1687	<i>Pongo pygmaeus</i>	Adult	Male	Wild-caught	Borneo	State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart, DE
2190	<i>Pongo pygmaeus</i>	Adult	Female	Wild-caught	Borneo, MY	State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart, DE
6286	<i>Pongo abelii</i>	Adult	Male	Wild-caught	Sumatra	Natural History Museum Basel, CH
7457	<i>Pongo pygmaeus</i>	Adult	Male	Wild-caught	Northern Borneo	State Museum of Natural History Stuttgart, DE

Abbreviations: CH = Switzerland; DE = Germany; DRC = Democratic Republic of the Congo; ID = Museum inventory numbers; JP = Japan; MY = Malaysia; US = The United States of America.

^a The bones of all individuals were fused, including specimens with unknown exact age, indicating adult or near-adult status.

^b Specimens were downloaded from Digital Morphology Museum of Kyoto University (KUPRI; <http://dmm.pri.kyoto-u.ac.jp/dmm/WebGallery/index.html>).

^c Specimens were downloaded from MorphoSource (<https://www.morphosource.org>).

Table 3
Details on *Australopithecus* sample (references are provided for the dating of the respective site).

Species	IDs	Date	Location	Institution	References
<i>Australopithecus afarensis</i>	A.L. 333w-39, A.L. 333-46, A.L. 333-62, A.L. 333-69, A.L. 333-89	~3.2 Ma	Hadar, Ethiopia	EHA, Ethiopia, and the Max Planck Society, Germany	Walter (1994)
<i>Australopithecus africanus</i>	StW 28, StW 63, StW 418, StW 331, StW 575	3.7–3.4 Ma	Sterkfontein, South Africa	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa	Granger et al. (2022)
<i>Australopithecus sediba</i>	U.W. 88-91, U.W. 88-118, U.W. 88-119, U.W. 88-121, U.W. 88-161	1.95–1.78 Ma	Malapa, South Africa	University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa	Pickering et al. (2011)

Abbreviations: EHA = Ethiopian Heritage Authority; IDs = Museum inventory numbers.

exception is the FDS attachment on the third intermediate phalanx (Fig. 2), used here to infer habitual arboreal activities. The attachment site on the third ray was chosen because this digit is actively used in arboreal behaviors (Samuel et al., 2018). In the case of *A. africanus*, we used the only intermediate phalanx found in Sterkfontein Member 4, likely of the second, third, or fourth ray (Kivell et al., 2020). Of the first (Fig. 3) and fifth ray (Fig. 4), we analyzed the attachment sites of the following muscles: on the first metacarpal: OP, abductor pollicis longus (APL), DI1; first proximal phalanx: abductor pollicis (ABP), flexor pollicis brevis (FPB), adductor pollicis (ADP); fifth metacarpal: extensor carpi ulnaris (ECU); fifth proximal phalanx: abductor digiti minimi (ADM), flexor digiti minimi (FDM). The majority of these muscles share corresponding attachments and functions among all investigated species. The DI1 is an exception as it is absent in *P. troglodytes* (but present in all other species, including the other great apes). Instead, this species presents a plesiomorphic state in which the intermediate metacarpals 1–4 are not fused with the flexores brevis profundi 3, 5, 6, and 8 to form the dorsal interossei (Diogo et al., 2012). Nonetheless, since the first intermetacarpalis attaches in a similar area as the DI1 (Diogo et al., 2013), it is suggested to have a similar function (Lemelin and Diogo, 2016; Vereecke and Wunderlich, 2016; van Leeuwen et al., 2018). Further differences in muscle function are reported for the OP as it functions as an adductor in

chimpanzees but as an abductor in humans (Marzke et al., 1999). Finally, the ABP and FPB muscles, as well as the ADM and FDM muscles, attach in a similar area of their respective bones so that their attachment sites are often indistinguishable (Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016). Therefore, we considered the surface area of the two entheses as one combined attachment site and referred to them as ABP-FPB and ADM-FDM throughout the study. More information on muscle origin, insertion, and function can be found in Table 4.

During data collection, wherever possible, we used bones from the right anatomical side for analysis, as this side appeared to be better preserved in our sample. However, the preservation of many of the fossil specimens required pooling anatomical sides for some individuals in order to analyze all relevant attachment sites. While this did not seem to affect the analyses (i.e., anatomical sides did not create any visual patterns in the plots), we additionally tested whether the anatomical side had an effect on principal component (PC) scores through analyses of variance (ANOVAs; Kruskal–Wallis tests were used if assumptions were violated). Additionally, the hand skeletons of *A. afarensis* and *A. africanus* used here are both composites. Consequently, the analysis uses bones from different individuals, which could potentially affect the results. Unfortunately, complete hand skeletons have not been found for either species to date, leaving composite hand skeletons as the only

Figure 1. Schematic depiction of the entheses used in the analysis on a human hand skeleton. Grevenmacher individual 117 (Paleoanthropology Human Osteology Collection, University of Tübingen) was used as a reference. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

option for analyses such as ours. A more thorough discussion of the potential effects of this procedure can be found in Section 4.3, Limitations.

2.2. Methods

Enthesis identification and delineation Delineation of the muscle attachment sites was performed on three-dimensional (3D) surface models of the bones. The process followed the VERA method (Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016; Karakostis et al., 2020; Karakostis and Harvati, 2021; Karakostis, 2023). The procedure will be briefly outlined here (for a more detailed description, see Karakostis et al., 2020; Karakostis and Harvati, 2021; Karakostis, 2023). The entheses were identified and delineated in Meshlab v. 2021.07 (Cignoni et al., 2008) using filters provided by the program (e.g., ‘Discrete Curvature’, ‘Equalize Vertex Colors’, ‘Principal Directions of Curvature’). These filters are used to identify differences in elevation—including depression and projection—coloration (in cases where color information was available in the 3D model) and surface complexity. After identification, the area of muscle

attachment was delineated and then separated from the remaining bone. Delineations were subsequently improved using the ‘Principal Directions of Curvature’ filter. Lastly, the 3D surface areas were measured in square millimeters using the ‘Compute Geometric Measures’ function.

Figures 5–7 depict the entheses delineations of the australopiths. To improve comparability in the images, bones from the left anatomical side were mirrored. Overall, most delineations following the VERA protocols were largely consistent with previous identifications of the area of muscle attachment (Kivell et al., 2011, 2018; Karakostis et al., 2021a; Kunze et al., 2022; but see *A. africanus*’ DI1 in Kivell et al., 2011; *A. sediba*’s OP in Kivell et al., 2011, 2018). Nevertheless, the identification and delineation of two specific entheses should be addressed in more detail. First, following previous studies (including those applying VERA), the insertion site of OP was represented in our analyses by the distal–lateral elevation of the first metacarpal bone. In humans, this elevation typically consists of a smooth tubercle that spans from the metacarpal head (below the articular surface) to the most distal shaft of the bone, from where it often—but not

Figure 2. Depiction of the flexor digitorum superficialis delineated on the right third intermediate phalanx of Basel STJ-0264 (left), recent modern human, and *Pan troglodytes* 51205 (right). a) Medial view; b) palmar view; c) lateral view. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

Figure 3. Enteses of the first ray. 1) Depiction of the enteses delineated on the right first metacarpal of Basel STJ-0264 (left), recent modern human, and *Pan troglodytes* 51205 (right). 1a) Medial view with the delineation of the first dorsal interosseus entesis; 1b) palmar view; 1c) lateral view with the delineations of the opponens pollicis and abductor pollicis longus enteses. 2) Depiction of the enteses delineated on the right first proximal phalanx of Basel STJ-0264 (left), recent modern human, and *Pan troglodytes* 51205 (right). 2a) Medial view with the delineation of the adductor pollicis entesis; 2b) palmar view; 2c) lateral view with delineation of the abductor pollicis–flexor pollicis brevis entesis. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

always—extends proximally in the form of a narrow ridge of variable length (e.g., see Maki and Trinkaus, 2011; Karakostis et al., 2018b). Previous anatomical and histological research conducted by one of us (FAK) involving the hand cadavers of body donors (Karakostis et al., 2019c, 2021a) confirmed that the OP muscle/tendon attached to both the proximal ridge and a substantial portion of the smooth tubercle below the head’s articular surface (including its most central portion; Karakostis et al., 2019c). The

fact that OP attaches to that part of the bone is also consistent with descriptions and cadaveric photographs in anatomical textbooks (e.g., Gosling et al., 2008; Lemelin and Diogo, 2016). Nevertheless, a considerable upper portion of this tubercle also acts as the attachment site of the radial collateral ligament. Considering that there is no clear distinction on the tubercle’s surface between the two exact attachment areas, our only option was to measure the 3D surface area of the entire structure as a whole (following standard

Figure 4. Entheses of the fifth ray. 1) Depiction of the entheses delineated on the right fifth metacarpal of Basel STJ-0264 (left), recent modern human, and *Pan troglodytes* 51205 (right). 1a) Medial view with the delineation of the extensor carpi ulnaris entheses; 1b) palmar view. 2) Depiction of the entheses delineated on the right fifth proximal phalanx of Basel STJ-0264 (left), recent modern human, and *Pan troglodytes* 51205 (right). 2a) Medial view with the delineation of the abductor digiti minimi–flexor digiti minimi entheses; 2b) palmar view. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

Table 4
Characteristics of muscles and attachment sites used in the analysis.

Muscle	Origin	Insertion	Muscle function
Opponens pollicis	Trapezium bone	Radial diaphysis of MC1	Abducts, rotates, and flexes the thumb
Abductor pollicis longus	Radius, ulna, scaphoid, trapezium, transverse carpal ligament	Base of MC1	Abducts and rotates the MC1 medially
First dorsal interosseus	MC1 and MC2 diaphyses	Base of PP2	Abducts the 2nd digit
Abductor pollicis brevis	Scaphoid, trapezium, flexor retinaculum	Base of PP1 (radial)	Abducts the thumb
Flexor pollicis brevis	Capitate, trapezium, flexor retinaculum	Base of PP1 (radial)	Flexes the thumb
Adductor pollicis	Palmar surface and base of MC3, base of MC2, capitate	Base of PP1 (ulnar)	Adducts the thumb at the MCP joint, flexes at the MCP joint
Extensor carpi ulnaris	Humerus, ulna	Base of MC5	Extends and adducts the hand
Abductor digiti minimi	Pisiform	Base of PP5 (ulnar) and dorsal digital expansion of 5th digit	Flexes and abducts 5th digit at MCP joint, extends at PIP and DIP joints
Flexor digiti minimi brevis	Hook of hamate, flexor retinaculum	Base of PP5 (ulnar)	Flexes the 5th digit
Flexor digitorum superficialis	Humerus, ulna, radius	Sides of intermediate phalanges of 2nd to 5th digits	Weak elbow flexion, flexes the wrist, MCP and PIP joints

Abbreviations: CMC = carpometacarpal; DIP = distal interphalangeal; MC = metacarpal; MCP = metacarpalphalangeal; PIP = proximal interphalangeal; PP = proximal phalanx.

VERA practice for distinct structures acting as the attachment sites of more than one soft tissue; e.g., see Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016; Karakostis et al., 2017; Karakostis and Harvati, 2021; Karakostis, 2023). This decision, which aligns with the strategy of all previous VERA studies, theoretically relies on the so-called ‘entheses

organ’ concept (Benjamin and McGonagle, 2009; see Karakostis and Harvati, 2021; Karakostis, 2023), according to which muscle forces are not expected to exclusively affect a muscle/tendon’s direct footprint (e.g., the center of the tubercle) but to dissipate to the surrounding tissues (including the part of the same continuous

Figure 5. Depiction of the flexor digitorum superficialis in medial, palmar, and lateral views delineated on the third intermediate phalanx of *Australopithecus africanus* (a, StW 331, right), *Australopithecus afarensis* (b, A.L. 333-46, right), and *Australopithecus sediba* (c, U.W. 88-161, right). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

Figure 6. Entheses of the first ray. Bones from the left anatomical side are mirrored. Depiction of the entheses delineated on the first metacarpal in medial (first dorsal interosseus), palmar, and lateral (opponens pollicis and abductor pollicis longus) views of *Australopithecus africanus* (a, StW 418, left), *Australopithecus afarensis* (b, A.L. 333 w-39, right), and *Australopithecus sediba* (c, U.W. 88-119, right). The opponens pollicis delineation of *Australopithecus sediba* includes both the versions without and with the isolated ridge on the lateral bone shaft. Depiction of the entheses delineated on the first proximal phalanx in medial (adductor pollicis), palmar, and lateral (abductor pollicis–flexor pollicis brevis) views of *Australopithecus africanus* (d, StW 575, right), *Australopithecus afarensis* (e, A.L.333-69, right), and *Australopithecus sediba* (f, U.W.88-91, left). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

bony tubercle that is associated with the ligament). Considering that humans typically combine thumb opposition with metacarpophalangeal flexion (performed via the contraction of OP’s synergist thenar muscles ABP, FPB, and ADP), the biomechanical forces from OP and the radial collateral ligament are expected to be closely correlated, providing an additional functional argument for measuring the entire tubercle as a representative of OP and thumb opposition movements in general.

Moreover, a few individuals (*A. sediba*, Ohalo 2, and Basel STJ-211) presented an additional midshaft ridge that is disconnected from the tubercle and the remaining enthesial surface (Fig. 6). Following VERA protocols, this disconnected area was initially not included. However, given that this narrow elevation might be an attachment site of the OP (see Kivell et al., 2011, 2018), we performed a second analysis including the surface area of the isolated midshaft ridge in the OP measurement of all individuals that presented this trait. Since that alternative delineation, which had a minimal impact on the final enthesial measurements of those individuals, led to no considerable change in any observed enthesial patterns of this study (including that of *A. sediba*), we decided to

keep the original delineations consistent with the established VERA protocols. Nevertheless, for any future reference, we have included a clear depiction of those alternative delineations on *A. sediba* in Figure 6.

A second notable delineation procedure concerns the FDS attachment site. The FDS muscle attaches in two separate regions of the bone. The muscle belly of the FDS separates into four tendons prior to inserting into the intermediate phalanges of rays two to five. Shortly before these tendons attach to the bone, they further separate into two strands each, connecting medially and laterally on the palmar surface of the intermediate phalanges (Netter et al., 2019). These attachment sites typically manifest as elevated ridges on each side of the bone, often accompanied by an adjacent, distinct depression or elevation. Here, we analyze the combined surface area of both attachment areas as we are interested in the more general use of the muscle and its main contribution to finger flexion, irrespective of whether the lateral or medial side of the attachment is more pronounced. Consequently, after the two attachment sites were delineated separately, their surface area measurements were added and treated as one attachment site.

Figure 7. Entheses of the fifth ray. Bones from the left anatomical side are mirrored. Depiction of the extensor carpi ulnaris entheses delineated on the fifth metacarpal in medial and palmar views of *Australopithecus africanus* (a, StW 63, left), *Australopithecus afarensis* (b, A.L. 333-89, left), and *Australopithecus sediba* (c, UW88-118, right). Depiction of the abductor digiti minimi–flexor digiti minimi entheses delineated on the fifth proximal phalanx in medial and palmar views of *Australopithecus africanus* (d, StW 28, right), *Australopithecus afarensis* (e, A.L. 333-62, left), and *Australopithecus sediba* (f, U.W. 88-121, right) (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

Given that the surface area measurements of entheses are affected by bone size and other systemic factors (e.g., Rauch, 2005; Milella et al., 2012; Foster et al., 2014), we adjusted the measurements before analyzing them further. For this, we used a combined two-step adjustment process based on both the total bone surface area (step 1) and the geometric mean (step 2).

First, great apes and humans have different finger-to-thumb ratios—the thumb is proportionally larger in humans, whereas great apes generally have comparatively longer fingers (e.g., Marzke and Wullstein, 1996; Tocheri et al., 2008; Almcija et al., 2015). Moreover, differences in bone size affect the size of its entheses, as larger bones will typically show bigger entheses. Consequently, if not corrected for, entheses located on the fifth ray will always be proportionally larger in nonhuman great apes than in humans as these species inherently have a proportionately larger fifth ray. Similarly, entheses of the first ray would always show higher proportions in humans, simply because they inherently have a proportionally larger thumb than great apes in comparison to the fifth ray. However, these enthesal differences will be primarily driven by genetically determined interspecies variation in finger-size proportions, which may be unrelated to each individual's lifetime loading history. To address this, we first divided each enthesal measurement by the total bone surface area of the bone it is located on (following Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016).

Nevertheless, even though adjusting the measurements using surface area accounts for differences in bone proportionality among species, it still does not account for the effects of variation in overall enthesal size among species and individuals. Species and individuals that tend to have overall larger entheses (e.g., gorillas) will still show greater enthesal proportions across the hand,

plotting as outliers (see paragraph below), irrespective of lifetime activity. To address this issue, the resulting values were additionally adjusted using the geometric mean (2nd step), which is a common step of the VERA protocols (e.g., Karakostis et al., 2017; Karakostis, 2023). Its application can be used not only to control for the effects of individual size but also for the effects of other extrinsic and intrinsic factors affecting interindividual variation in enthesal surface area (Karakostis et al., 2017, 2019a, 2021b; Karakostis and Harvati, 2021). We calculated the geometric mean for each individual separately using the sum of all enthesal measurements (after correction step one). Subsequently, all enthesal measurements are divided by the geometric mean that was calculated for that individual. Through this procedure, we can assess the proportions of the entheses among each other, indicating whether an enthesal surface is relatively large or small compared to other enthesal surfaces within the same individual (see Karakostis, 2023).

It should be noted that this is the first study to propose a two-step adjustment procedure (building upon the statistical protocol published in Karakostis, 2023) since this is the first VERA analysis that compares species with extensively different ray proportions. Therefore, in the following paragraphs, we aim to demonstrate the value of this approach by discussing the results when performing only adjustment steps one or two, respectively. We included the results using data only adjusted with surface area measurements in the Supplements (i.e., the results after performing only adjustment step one; Supplementary Online Material [SOM] Figs. S1–S3; Tables S1 and S2). When only correcting for proportionality (based on the bone surface area), our core observations are still present, but the analyses appear to be affected by interindividual overall size differences (see exclusively positive PC1 loadings in the

analysis without FDS; SOM Table S1) and the resulting presence of outliers (see two *G. gorilla* individuals in the analysis with FDS; SOM Figs. S2 and S3). Moreover, the loadings of the analyses do not differ significantly between the two adjustment procedures (see SOM Tables S1 and S2). However, in the first analysis (without FDS), adjusting with the geometric mean leads to a higher correlation of enthesal patterns with the variance depicted in the analysis, as shown by the overall higher loadings (SOM Fig. S1 and Table S1 compared to Fig. 8 and Table 5). In the second analysis (with FDS), applying the second adjustment step condenses the information depicted on three PCs into two (SOM Figs. S2 and S3; Table S2 compared to Fig. 9 and Table 6).

In contrast, when only adjusting using the geometric mean, the results of our analyses appear to be misleading. In particular, when the extensive interspecies differences in ray bone proportionality are not accounted for, the multivariate analysis presents all nonhuman great apes to always have proportionally much larger entheses of the fifth ray (ADM-FDM and ECU). This contradicts morphological observations of the samples themselves as the fifth ray entheses of all great apes are distinctively much less developed (in proportion to bone size) and flatter than those of later *Homo* (Fig. 7). This striking discrepancy can be fully explained by the fact that ray proportions greatly vary between humans and other great apes. Essentially, although the fifth ray entheses clearly cover a much smaller area of the bone in great apes, their raw surface still appears relatively larger than in humans simply because the associated bones are comparatively much bigger overall (especially when adjusted using the entheses of their comparatively much smaller thumb bones). Consequently, when only adjusting with the

geometric mean, the results are exclusively driven by differences in ray proportionality among species and clearly do not reflect differences in habitual activity.

Overall, based on the aforementioned observations and results, we consider the aforementioned two-step adjustment procedure to be the most appropriate approach for the objectives of this study. **Precision test** The delineation of the entheses of a small but representative proportion of the sample ($n = 5$) was repeated at least two months after the initial delineation by the same observer (JK) to test for intraobserver error. The subsample included one individual each of early and recent *H. sapiens*, *H. neanderthalensis*, *A. sediba*, and *A. africanus*. The deviation of the repetitions, obtained by calculating the percentage of the standard deviation divided by the mean, was consistently below 5% (mean = 2.45%, minimum = 0.09%, maximum = 4.80%), suggesting a high precision of the delineation procedure, as previously reported for the VERA measuring protocols (e.g., Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016; Castro et al., 2022; Kunze et al., 2022). Additionally, we further assessed repeatability error using Lin's concordance coefficient, whose values were consistently above 0.99 (out of 1.00) across entheses and species, indicating near-perfect measuring repeatability (McBride, 2005; Karakostis, 2023).

Statistical analysis For the analyses, two subsamples were created. The first included all individuals but a reduced number of attachment sites (without FDS enthesal measurement). In order to include the FDS attachment site measurement in the second subsample, the sample size had to be reduced. In particular, due to preservation or limited access, we could not measure the FDS enthesal site in *Pongo abelii* 6286, *Gorilla gorilla* 6294, *Pan troglodytes*

Figure 8. Bivariate plot of the first and second principal components (PC1 and PC2) for the analysis on size-adjusted enthesal measurements without a priori group association. Flexor digitorum superficialis attachment site measurements are not included. Captive great apes are indicated with an asterisk. Abbreviations: AC = Arene Candide; OH = Ohalo; Q = Qafzeh; KB = Kebara; LF = La Ferrassie; SH = Shanidar. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

Table 5
Eigenvalues and factor loadings of principal components (PCs) 1–4 of the analysis of enthesal proportions, not including flexor digitorum superficialis measurements.

Principal component ^a	Eigenvalue	Percentage of variance	Factor loadings						
			OP	APL	DI1	ABP-FPB	ADP	ECU	ADM-FDM
PC1	2.45	35	0.42	0.32	-0.82	0.75	0.70	-0.40	-0.54
PC2	1.48	21.09	-0.40	-0.59	-0.37	0.22	0.50	0.60	0.40
PC3	1.11	15.79	-0.72	0.34	0.17	0.45	-0.01	-0.40	0.30
PC4	0.85	12.15	0.14	0.57	-0.38	-0.01	-0.26	0.37	0.40

Abbreviations: ABP-FPB = abductor pollicis–flexor pollicis brevis; ADM-FDM = abductor digiti minimi–flexor digiti minimi; ADP = adductor pollicis; APL = abductor pollicis longus; DI1 = first dorsal interosseus; ECU = extensor carpi radialis; OP = opponens pollicis; PC = principal component.

^a Only depicts PCs that are used for analysis.

Figure 9. Bivariate plot of the first and second principal components (PC1 and PC2) for the analysis on size-adjusted enthesal measurements without a priori group association. Flexor digitorum superficialis attachment site measurements are included. Captive great apes are indicated with an asterisk. Abbreviations: OH = Ohalo; Q = Qafzeh; KB = Kebara; LF = La Ferrassie. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

Table 6
Eigenvalues and factor loadings of principal components (PCs) 1–3 of the analysis of enthesal proportions, including flexor digitorum superficialis measurements.

Principal component ^a	Eigenvalue	Percentage of variance	Factor loadings							
			OP	APL	DI1	ABP-FPB	ADP	ECU	ADM-FDM	FDS
PC1	2.91	36.37	0.44	0.21	-0.82	0.56	0.59	-0.52	-0.75	0.71
PC2	1.57	19.67	-0.62	-0.36	-0.38	0.49	0.58	0.46	0.38	-0.07
PC3	1.22	15.24	-0.25	0.72	-0.04	0.47	-0.13	-0.41	0.24	-0.41

Abbreviations: ABP-FPB = abductor pollicis–flexor pollicis brevis; ADM-FDM = abductor digiti minimi–flexor digiti minimi; ADP = adductor pollicis; APL = abductor pollicis longus; DI1 = first dorsal interosseus; ECU = extensor carpi radialis; FDS = flexor digitorum superficialis; OP = opponens pollicis; PC = principal component.

^a Only depicts PCs that are used for analysis.

10824 and 51376, Arene Candide 2, Shanidar 4, and Grevenmacher individual 105. These individuals were therefore excluded from the second subsample.

Principal component analyses (PCAs) based on a correlation matrix were performed on both subsamples. The australopiths were not included in the initial analyses but were later projected

into the PC plot using the 'project' function in RStudio v. 2022.12.0 (Posit Team, 2022 with R v. 4.2.2; R Core Team, 2021). The later *Homo* fossil specimens were analyzed together with the recent sample and not projected in order to capture a broad range of human manual behavior, encompassing both manual activities of recent humans as well as activities more comparable to those of early hominins (e.g., stone tool production and use). The absence of extreme outliers was confirmed using a z-score approach (Field, 2017). While there was one extreme value (>3.29) in both subsamples (after projection), the frequency percentages were as expected for a normal distribution (see Field, 2017). Moreover, the individual showing extreme z-scores (*A. sediba*) was not included in the actual calculation of the components, supporting the absence of influential outliers.

In addition to the PCAs, we applied two discriminant function analyses (DFAs) using the adjusted measurements as variables. The sample was divided into two groups: the first comprised individuals of the genus *Homo*, whereas the second included all nonhuman great apes. The early hominins were entered with unknown group membership. The DFA aimed to identify the variables that best distinguish between the two groups and classify the *Australopithecus* specimens based on these variables. The analyses were performed in SPSS v. 28.0.1.0 (IBM Corp., 2017). Since the Box's M test for the first dataset (without FDS) was nonsignificant, indicating equal covariance matrices, a within-group covariance matrix was used for the analysis (Field, 2017). The Box's M test for the second dataset (with FDS) was statistically significant. To determine the cause and assess the effect on our analysis, we pursued different strategies. First, we ran the DFA using a separate-group covariance matrix. Secondly, we transformed our data using log transformation and the z-score approach. Finally, we conducted Levene's test of homogeneity of variances and a test of multivariate normality. The test of multivariate normality was not statistically significant. In contrast, Levene's test produced significant results for the OP and ADM-FDM measurements, suggesting that variances were not homogenous among groups for those measurements. To assess the effect of these variables on the results, they were removed in the next step. However, none of the aforementioned adjustments appeared to have affected the results. In all cases, the Box's M test remained significant, and, more importantly, the comparative sample of later *Homo* and great apes showed the same classification rates (100%). This was also the case when a separate-group covariance matrix was used, which is not affected by the violation of Box's M. Based on this finding and the common practice that Box's M can be disregarded when group sizes are equal (Field, 2017; later *Homo* = 14, great apes = 15), we decided to use a within-group covariance matrix for the analysis. The variables were entered stepwise, and the leave-one-out classification method was chosen. In both analyses, the stepwise approach identified the adjusted measurements of the DI1, ECU, and ADM-FDM attachment sites to provide the best separation between the groups, so these variables were retained in the analysis.

3. Results

3.1. Analyses excluding the flexor digitorum superficialis

Based on the ANOVAs, the anatomical side had no significant effect on the analysis ($p > 0.05$). In the first analysis (without the FDS measurements, Fig. 8; SOM Figs. S4 and S5; Table 5), the variation in muscle attachment site proportions clearly distinguishes later *Homo* from nonhuman great apes. The two groups are separated on PC1 (explaining 35.00% of variance in the sample; Fig. 8), with later *Homo* displaying negative PC1 values (with only one exception) and great apes showing positive values. The

enthesal pattern shared by individuals with positive PC1 loadings includes proportionally large ADP, ABP-FPB, OP, and APL entheses. In contrast, the pattern associated with PC1-negative values combines a proportionally large DI1 with large ECU and ADM-FDM attachment sites. The second PC (21.09% of variance) does not contribute to the separation between later *Homo* and great apes as they overlap extensively on this axis. Generally, all groups overlap on this component, showing no genus-, species-, or population-related distinction. The enthesal pattern on PC2-positive is characterized by proportionally large attachment sites of the ECU, ADM-FDM, ADP, and ABP-FPB, whereas the pattern on PC2-negative entails relatively large DI1, OP, and APL entheses. All australopiths show an enthesal pattern more similar to later *Homo* than to great apes, although only *A. africanus* falls inside their convex hull in this plot. *Australopithecus africanus* combines a proportionately large OP attachment site that is comparatively more apelike with a relatively large ECU attachment site that is more humanlike (Figs. 6 and 7). While *A. sediba* overlaps with recent modern humans on PC1, it exceeds the range of variation of all later *Homo* groups and nonhuman great apes on PC2 considerably, due to its extreme positive value. This unique position on PC2 is caused by its proportionally large attachment sites of the fifth ray (ECU and ADM-FDM), particularly when compared to its relatively small OP and APL attachment sites (Figs. 6 and 7). *Australopithecus afarensis* plots closer to the center of PC1 while still overlapping with later *Homo* on this component and close to their convex hull on PC2. *Australopithecus afarensis* combines a proportionately small OP enthesal site with relatively large attachment sites of the first proximal phalanx. Moreover, its DI1 attachment site proportion is more intermediate between that of later *Homo* and great apes, likely explaining its position closer to the center of PC1 (Fig. 6).

The enthesal pattern on PC3-negative (15.79% of variance; SOM Fig. S4) consists of proportionally large ECU, OP, and ADP attachment sites, whereas individuals with PC3-positive values show relatively large DI1, ADM-FDM, APL, and ABP-FPB entheses. Plotting PC3 against PC1 shows the *Gorilla* group expanding further toward being PC3 negative than the other great apes. However, this deviation from *Pan* and *Pongo* is mainly caused by one *Gorilla* individual showing unusually low values on this component. The remaining groups consistently overlap on PC3. While *A. sediba* still shows the highest positive value on this axis, it plots slightly closer to the range of variation of later *Homo* and nonhuman great ape genera on PC3. Additionally, *A. afarensis* plots inside the convex hull of later *Homo*, whereas *A. africanus* is positioned outside of it.

On PC4 (12.15% of variance; SOM Fig. S5), only proportionally large DI1 and ADP attachment sites are associated with negative loadings, whereas the remaining entheses (ABP-FPB, ADM-FDM, ECU, APL, OP) are correlated with positive values. Neither does this component contribute to the separation of later *Homo* and great apes, nor does it distinguish between the great apes, but similar to PC3, it affects the position of the australopiths, which all have positive loadings on this axis. *Australopithecus sediba* is positioned closer to the group of later *Homo* than in previous plots, whereas *A. afarensis* and *A. africanus* plot outside their convex hull.

Supporting the results of the PCA, the DFA (Table 7) identified the proportionate surface area of the DI1, ADM, and ECU entheses as the variables providing the best separation of the two groups (later *Homo* and great apes). Based on these variables, 100% of the original grouped cases were correctly classified (Table 8). Among the australopiths, *A. afarensis* and *A. sediba* are classified as later *Homo* with a posterior probability of 79.6% and 100%, respectively (Table 9). In contrast, *A. africanus* was classified as a great ape with a posterior probability of 67.98%. These results are visualized in Figure 10, in which the discriminant scores are plotted for each group separately. Later *Homo* consistently shows positive scores,

Table 7
Canonical discriminant function coefficient of the discriminant function analyses (DFAs).

Analysis 1		Analysis 2	
DI1	5.05	DI1	5.57
ECU	2.62	ECU	3.94
ADM-FDM	5.36	ADM-FDM	5.65
Constant	-14.16	Constant	-14.84

Abbreviations: ADM-FDM = abductor digiti minimi–flexor digiti minimi; DI1 = first dorsal interosseus; ECU = extensor carpi radialis.

Table 8
Statistics of the discriminant function analyses (DFAs).

DFA	Humans		Great apes		Group centroid	
	Original	Cross-validated	Original	Cross-validated	Humans	Great apes
Analysis 1	100	94.1	100	100	2.48	2.22
Analysis 2	100	100	100	100	2.94	2.74

Abbreviation: DFA = discriminant function analysis.

whereas great apes display negative scores. *Australopithecus afarensis* and *A. africanus* plot between the two groups, with the latter closer to great apes and the former closer to later *Homo*. In contrast, *A. sediba* exhibits the highest discriminant scores in the sample, placing it above the later *Homo* group.

3.2. Analyses including the flexor digitorum superficialis

In the next step, the FDS measurements were added to the analysis (Fig. 9; SOM Fig. S6; Table 6). Both PC1 and PC2 are not significantly affected by anatomical side ($p > 0.05$), whereas anatomical side appears to influence PC3 ($p = 0.03$). The loadings on PC1 (36.37% of variance; Fig. 9) are similar to the previous analysis. In addition, the FDS attachment site proportions highly correlate with the variation on PC1, with individuals plotting toward PC1-positive values showing a proportionally large FDS entheses. As in the previous PCA, great apes exclusively present positive PC1 values; all but one *Pongo* individual present values above 1 on this axis. The later *Homo* group has negative PC1 values, leading to an increased separation between them and the great apes. The loadings on PC2 (19.67% of variance) are also similar to those of the first analysis as the FDS surface area proportions are only slightly correlated with PC2-negative values (-0.07 , Table 6). Nonetheless, including the FDS entheses measurements indirectly impacted either the entheses proportions of the remaining entheses or the factor loadings of the analysis, leading to a separation of the great apes on PC2 that is not seen in the analysis without the FDS. While *Pan* and *Gorilla* show similar values, *Pongo* specimens exhibit higher positive PC2 values than most individuals from the other two genera. Positive PC2 values are associated with proportionately large attachment sites on the first proximal

Table 9
Predicted group and posterior probability values of the discriminant function analyses (DFAs).^a

Species	Analysis 1		Analysis 2		Analysis 2 log ^b	
	Predicted group	Posterior probability	Predicted group	Posterior probability	Predicted group	Posterior probability
<i>Australopithecus africanus</i>	Great ape	0.68	Great ape	0.83	Later <i>Homo</i>	0.84
<i>Australopithecus sediba</i>	Later <i>Homo</i>	1	Later <i>Homo</i>	1	Later <i>Homo</i>	1
<i>Australopithecus afarensis</i>	Later <i>Homo</i>	0.8				

^a Later *Homo* comprises *Homo sapiens* and *Homo neanderthalensis*.

^b Results if size-adjusted entheses measurements are log-transformed prior to the analysis (see Methods).

Figure 10. Results of the discriminant function analysis on size-adjusted entheses measurements without the flexor digitorum superficialis entheses measurements. Groups are depicted on the x-axis; discriminant scores are depicted on the y-axis (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

phalanx and the fifth ray, whereas negative values indicate large entheses proportions of the first metacarpal. Among the australopithecids, *A. sediba* shares the humanlike configuration on PC1 but shows a more positive value than later *Homo* on PC2. In contrast, *A. africanus* and *A. afarensis* plot in between later *Homo* and the great apes on PC1, although slightly closer to the former. This more intermediate position of these two specimens compared to the previous analysis is at least partially caused by the increased separation of later *Homo* and great apes on PC1 as these groups plot further away from the center of the plot than in the previous PCA, whereas *A. afarensis* and *A. africanus* maintain a similar position. Moreover, in the case of *A. afarensis* in particular, the shift toward the great apes in comparison to the previous analysis is also caused by its proportionately large FDS attachment site (Fig. 5). On PC2, *A. africanus* overlaps with recent modern humans as well as *Pan* and *Gorilla* specimens, whereas *A. afarensis* overlaps with *Pongo* and later *Homo* on this component.

PC3 (15.24% of variance; SOM Fig. S6) shows more overlap among the great apes. The entheses pattern associated with the loadings on PC3-negative includes proportionately large entheses of DI1, ECU, FDS, OP, and ADP, whereas PC3 positive exhibits a high

Figure 11. Results of the discriminant function analysis on size-adjusted enthesal measurements with the flexor digitorum superficialis measurements. Groups are depicted on the x-axis; discriminant scores are depicted on the y-axis. A: discriminant function analysis based on within-group covariance matrix; B: discriminant function analysis using log-transformed variables. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

Figure 12. Boxplot of the size-adjusted flexor digitorum superficialis (FDS) enthesal measurements for the groups of the comparative sample (later *Homo* and the great ape genera), *Australopithecus afarensis*, *Australopithecus africanus*, and *Australopithecus sediba*/ (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article).

correlation with the relative size of the APL attachment site and, to a lesser degree, with ADM-FDM and ABP-FPB attachment site proportions. *Australopithecus sediba* and *A. africanus* both show negative values on this component, whereas *A. afarensis* has low positive values. As in the previous plot, *A. africanus* and *A. afarensis* are positioned between later *Homo* and great apes. On PC3, all

australopiths overlap with later *Homo*, *Gorilla*, and *Pan*, but only *A. sediba* and *A. afarensis* overlap with *Pongo*. Moreover, *A. sediba*'s PC3 value places it inside the convex hull of later *Homo*. Importantly, interpretations based on the variation displayed on this axis should be treated with caution due to the previously mentioned effect of anatomical side on PC3.

The DFA, using the proportionate surface area of the DI1, ADM-FDM, and ECU as variables, separates later *Homo* and great apes with an accuracy of 100% (original and cross-validation; Tables 7 and 8). *Australopithecus sediba* is classified as later *Homo* with a posterior probability of 100% (Table 9). In contrast, the classifications of *A. africanus* and *A. afarensis* are less straightforward. As stated in Section 2.2 earlier, the DFA including the FDS measurements was carried out multiple times using different matrices and transformed variables. While this procedure did not affect the overall accuracy of the analysis or the classification of *A. sediba*, it strongly affected the classification of *A. africanus* and *A. afarensis*. When using a within-group covariance matrix or analyzing z-scores of the original measurements, both are classified as a nonhuman great ape (*A. africanus*: 82.94%, *A. afarensis*: 73.0% posterior probability). However, when the DFA is based on a separate-group covariance matrix or when the variables are log-transformed, they are classified as later *Homo* (*A. africanus*: 90.05%/84.4%, *A. afarensis*: 94.82%/91.6% posterior probability, respectively). Plotting the discriminant scores sheds light on this issue. Figure 11 shows the discriminant scores when using a within-group covariance matrix in the left panel, whereas the right panel depicts the scores when analyzing log-transformed variables. In both cases, *A. africanus* and *A. afarensis* plot in between later *Homo* and great apes, shifting only slightly toward positive or negative discriminant scores. Therefore, we conclude that both *A. africanus*' and *A. afarensis*' DI1, ECU, and ADM-FDM enthesal proportions are intermediate between those of later *Homo* and great apes, which causes slight changes to the analysis to impact their classification, whereas all other individuals are unaffected.

4. Discussion

4.1. Enthesal patterns of *Homo* and extant great apes

In agreement with our expectations, later *Homo* and great apes clearly differ in their enthesal patterns as revealed in our PCAs. Moreover, as hypothesized, the pattern characterizing the later *Homo* sample includes proportionally large DI1, ADM-FDM, and ECU attachment sites. The variation observed between human and nonhuman great apes on the PC1 axes is consistent with the proportional differences shown in the representative example illustrations of Figures 2–4, which show the proportionally larger 5th ray and DI1 enthesal areas in humans, despite the impressively larger fifth metacarpal bone of nonhuman great apes. In our previous study focusing on the first metacarpal's enthesal patterns, the DI1 enthesal proportions clearly differ between later *Homo* and nonhuman great apes (Kunze et al., 2022). Those results are confirmed here. The DI1 abducts the second digit (Netter et al., 2019) and stabilizes the thumb (Marzke et al., 1998). Electromyographic research has reported that the DI1 is highly activated during different types of tool use (Key et al., 2020) and hard-hammer percussion manufacture of stone tools (Marzke et al., 1998). Here, a proportionally large attachment site of this muscle is associated with relatively large entheses of the fifth ray. This digit and the muscles attaching to it are known to play important roles in tool production and use (Marzke and Shackley, 1986; Marzke et al., 1998; Marzke, 2013; Kivell, 2015; Key et al., 2019; Fedato et al., 2020). During hard-hammer percussion, the fifth digit of the nondominant hand is mainly involved in handling, orienting, and stabilizing the core against the impact force of the hammerstone. These activities involve high activation levels of the ADM and FDM, which abduct and flex the fifth digit, respectively, at the metacarpophalangeal joint (Marzke et al., 1998). The ADM additionally acts during tool use, mainly when tools of larger size, such as handaxes, are used (Key et al., 2020). The ECU, on the other hand, is one of the major extensor muscles of the wrist. Wrist extension in the dominant hand is crucial during knapping, as it stabilizes the wrist in the downswing phase and provides a mechanical advantage for the flexors (Williams et al., 2010, 2014).

However, the importance of the fifth digit and these three muscles is not limited to tool production and use. Previous research on enthesal patterns has shown that the ADM, FDM, and ECU are frequently activated in individuals whose profession during life required a high amount of power grasping (Karakostis et al., 2017; also see Marzke et al., 1992; Goislard de Monsabert et al., 2012). The ECU coactivates with the flexor carpi ulnaris to deviate the wrist in the ulnar direction, which is essential in power grasping of and striking with cylindrical objects (Marzke et al., 1992). Moreover, wrist extension, as induced by the ECU, is needed when throwing an object (Young, 2003). Power grips have also been reported to involve activation of the DI1 (Long II et al., 1970). In addition, the DI1, ADM, and FDM appear to be essential for the stabilization and in-hand manipulation of objects, including, among others, stone cores (Marzke et al., 1998; Marzke, 2013; Kivell, 2015; Key et al., 2019). Generally, in-hand manipulation and repositioning of objects are less frequent in great apes and are usually carried out by movements within the palm without engaging the fingertips (Christel, 1993; Bardo et al., 2017). As our later *Homo* sample spans a broad chronological and geographical range, we propose that their enthesal pattern may be attributed to more general humanlike hand use, instead of being explicitly indicative of tool use. Individuals depicting these enthesal proportions would, therefore, have habitually engaged in activities involving power grasping and humanlike in-hand manipulation, involving stabilization and control of objects with one hand.

In contrast, the pattern characterizing great apes consists of proportionally large attachment sites of OP, APL, ADP, ABP-FPB, and, when included, FDS. Most of these muscles are involved in thumb abduction and adduction. We expected the attachment sites of thumb adduction muscles to be associated with the great ape pattern as they perform movements that are essential for great ape grasping techniques (Christel, 1993). Notably, the OP reportedly serves as a flexor and adductor in chimpanzees, contrasting its function as an abductor in humans (Marzke et al., 1999). While not occurring frequently, thumb abduction and opposition have been observed during vertical climbing in chimpanzees and mountain gorillas (Neufuss et al., 2017), and all great apes have been reported to use thumb opposition to some degree when manipulating objects (Tuttle, 1969; Christel, 1993; Marzke and Wullstein, 1996; Marzke et al., 2015; Neufuss et al., 2019). The proportionally large FDS attachment site indicates habitual finger flexion, which was expected, given that this movement plays a critical role in arboreal locomotion (Susman and Stern, 1979). All in all, while some of the muscles associated with the great ape enthesal pattern on PC1 are related to specific great ape behaviors, the contribution of others, specifically OP, APL, and ABP-FPB, is more difficult to interpret. Generally, muscles contributing to thumb opposition (involving thumb abduction and flexion) would be expected to play a more important role in humanlike rather than in apelike hand use. This apparent inconsistency with general expectations and reported great ape behavior can be explained in different ways. First, due to the lack of detailed studies on how and to what extent muscles of the hand contribute to varying great ape activities (Bardo et al., 2017), we cannot exclude that these muscles are more heavily involved in great ape hand use than previously thought. Alternatively, the separation of later *Homo* and great apes reflected on PC1 of our analyses could be mainly driven by the human enthesal pattern that includes muscles with high functional relevance for humans but less so for great ape behavior. Following this interpretation, the great ape pattern would mainly consist of muscle attachment sites that, unlike DI1, ADM-FDM, and ECU entheses, are not relatively larger in humans. Therefore, instead of signifying functional relevance, the ape-like pattern might simply be neutral in comparison to the distinctive humanlike pattern of entheses and manipulation. The results of the DFA seem to support this possible interpretation as the analysis correctly classifies later *Homo* and great apes based only on the attachment site proportions of the human enthesal pattern (DI1, ABP-FPB, ECU). However, the PCA also shows an increased separation of later *Homo* and great apes when including the FDS attachment site, a muscle often associated with great ape behavior, suggesting that the enthesal pattern of great apes might also be partly associated with their behavioral trends (also see in the following).

When including the FDS enthesal measurements in the PCA, our PC2 axis shows a slight separation among great ape taxa (Fig. 9). Compared to most *Gorilla gorilla* and *Pan troglodytes* specimens, *Pongo pygmaeus* individuals present larger enthesal proportions of ADP, ABP-FPB, ADM-FDM, and ECU, whereas the other two species show relatively larger DI1, APL, OP, and FDS attachment sites. While it was expected that enthesal patterns would generally differ among the great ape taxa, as they engage in varying modes of locomotion and manipulation, we did not expect a proportionally large FDS attachment site to contribute to the enthesal patterns of *Gorilla* and *Pan*, but not to that of *Pongo* (Fig. 9), whose locomotion is largely arboreal and thus likely involves increased finger flexion. However, it must be highlighted here that the PC2 loading of FDS is almost zero (-0.07), suggesting that the observed differences between nonhuman great ape species are almost exclusively driven by the relative recruitment of other muscles (reflected on enthesal proportions). In particular, the positive PC2 values of our *Pongo*

specimens represent proportionally greater covariance among specific muscles of the first and fifth rays (Table 6). This could be related to the fact that arboreal species show high posture variability, leading to frequent readjustment of grips and high inter-variability in grasping techniques. Additionally, orangutans often use their mouth or feet to reposition tools, thereby freeing a hand to grasp branches (Bardo et al., 2017). Finally, great apes' hand and wrist morphology also shows notable differences among species. Compared to the African apes, *Pongo* is capable of greater wrist extension (85% compared to 42–76%; Rose, 1988; Sarmiento, 1988; Orr, 2017), potentially enabling more frequent use of the ECU. *Pongo* also possesses the shortest thumb among great apes (Bardo et al., 2018), which likely affects their thumb involvement in grasping, particularly in techniques requiring thumb opposition (Almécija et al., 2015; Feix et al., 2015). To summarize, while the variation of enthesal patterns depicted by the PCA does not appear to be associated with differences in great ape locomotion per se, it likely displays variation in grasping (both during locomotion and manipulation) that is caused by different modes of locomotion or habitat preferences. Unfortunately, interpreting the nonhuman primate enthesal pattern on a more detailed level is difficult as our knowledge of muscle activities and muscular coordination in their manipulatory behavior is limited (Bardo et al., 2017). Therefore, in order to substantiate a functional interpretation, further primatological and biomechanical research is required on the exact muscle coordination and grasping habits of great apes and particularly *Pongo*. Finally, the lack of correlation between the FDS enthesal pattern presented by the great apes in the PCA does not mean that there is no association between FDS attachment site proportion and degree of arboreality in our sample. Figure 12 shows a box plot depicting the adjusted FDS enthesal size per group (later *Homo* and each of the great ape genera). As is visible in the plot, FDS attachment site proportions increase with increasing arboreality: later *Homo* presents the smallest (on average) FDS entheses, whereas *P. pygmaeus* shows the largest. Consequently, while the arboreality trend is seemingly visible in the data, it is not correlated with the main axes of variance on PCs 1 to 3, which are mainly driven by the humanlike pattern of entheses (closely reflecting humanlike manipulation). In future research, by increasing the number of muscles that are actively involved in great ape locomotion, this trend may likely become more discernible.

4.2. Functional interpretation of early hominin enthesal patterns

In accordance with our expectations, the enthesal pattern of *A. sediba* is most distinct from that of great apes. However, while it shows similarities to later *Homo*, the pattern also includes distinctive proportions that separate *A. sediba* from all other individuals in the analysis: it combines a relatively large DI1 muscle attachment site with uniquely large enthesal proportions of the muscles attaching to the fifth ray and the first proximal phalanx. This unique position is not only caused by these large attachment sites but also by the distinctive contrast in size among *A. sediba*'s hand entheses in general. *Australopithecus sediba* presents large entheses of the fifth ray combined with very small entheses of OP and APL (Figs. 6 and 7). These unusual enthesal proportions, in combination with the loadings of the PCs (see Table 5), result in *A. sediba* diverging from the other individuals in our analyses. Despite these extreme proportions, its enthesal pattern suggests humanlike hand use, including power grasping, in-hand manipulation, and, potentially, tool use. Particularly, the fifth digit in the form of the ADM, FDM, and ECU muscles appears to play an essential role in *A. sediba*'s habitual manipulative behaviors. Previous work on *A. sediba*'s hand bones has pointed out its distinct morphology, including an unusually long thumb and a robust fifth

metacarpal (Kivell et al., 2018). Because of these and other derived traits, researchers have suggested that *A. sediba* was capable of more humanlike manipulative behavior (Kivell et al., 2018; Dunmore et al., 2020a). However, the retention of apelike traits in its hand (Kivell et al., 2018; Dunmore et al., 2020a) and its upper limb in general (Churchill et al., 2013, 2018; Rein et al., 2017) provides evidence for adaptations to climbing and suspensory locomotion and indicates that *A. sediba* could have used its hand for both humanlike manipulation and apelike locomotion (Kivell et al., 2018, 2023; Dunmore et al., 2020a). Our previous analysis of muscle attachment sites of the first metacarpal has found evidence for humanlike thumb use in *A. sediba* (MH2) and even suggested potential humanlike tool use in this individual (Kunze et al., 2022). Our current results on a wider range of entheses further support habitual humanlike hand use in *A. sediba*. While the enthesal pattern observed here should not be solely attributed to tool production and use, it shows a high involvement of intrinsic musculature and the muscles of the fifth digit, which are known to be crucial for these activities. In contrast, the enthesal pattern of *A. sediba* does not indicate habitual hand use in arboreal contexts as it distinctively differs from that of the arboreal great apes in our sample. However, the adjusted FDS enthesal measurements (see Fig. 12) could potentially suggest a frequent activation of the extrinsic flexor, which could be an indicator of habitual climbing or clambering (as has been suggested by other work on the *A. sediba* forelimb, e.g., Rein et al., 2017). It should be noted that only one of the muscles included in our study (FDS) reflects arboreal behaviors. Our analysis is, therefore, likely not suited to reliably trace signs of arboreal locomotion. Future studies should focus on muscles that are clearly associated with arboreal behaviors by expanding the analysis to the entheses of *A. sediba*'s upper limb.

Interpreting the enthesal pattern of the other two australopithecines is less straightforward. The enthesal pattern of *A. africanus* is intermediate between later *Homo* and nonhuman great apes, but its position relative to these two groups varies depending on the analysis. Without the FDS enthesal measurement, the PCA positions it closer to later *Homo*, providing potential evidence for some level of humanlike manipulation in *A. africanus*. However, this is contrasted by the result of the DFA that classifies it as a great ape. When the FDS measurement is included, *A. africanus*' enthesal pattern is intermediate between the two groups in both analyses. Particularly in the DFA, its classification changes when analysis parameters are altered (see Section 2), whereas most of the remaining sample, including *A. sediba*, provides the same results. Examinations of its hand morphology have led previous researchers to conclude that *A. africanus* was likely capable of performing precision and power-squeeze grips (Ricklan, 1987; Marzke, 2013). Furthermore, although the trabecular bone fraction in its metacarpals indicates a high load on the hands, the trabecular bone distribution is more similar to the tool-using species *H. sapiens* and *H. neanderthalensis* (Skinner et al., 2015). In contrast, our analysis of the entheses of the first metacarpal has suggested a more apelike thumb use in *A. africanus* as its pattern is most similar to *G. gorilla* (Kunze et al., 2022; also see Green and Gordon, 2008; Marchi et al., 2017; Galletta et al., 2019; Dunmore et al., 2020a for reports of more apelike hand-bone morphology). Our present study cannot fully support or refute either of these interpretations as the enthesal pattern of *A. africanus* is not consistently similar to either later *Homo* or extant great apes. Its unique enthesal pattern could potentially represent a unique manual behavior that differs from all other species in our comparative sample. However, considering the results of previous research, as well as the contradicting signals found here, we conclude that the enthesal pattern of *A. africanus* may represent a mosaic of humanlike and apelike manual behaviors. The exact nature of these behaviors is difficult to ascertain. On

the one hand, its enthesal pattern seems to indicate some degree of humanlike hand use involving power grasping and in-hand manipulation. On the other hand, the analyses also show a divergence from the human pattern in the direction of apelike hand use. It could be argued that including the FDS entheses causes *A. africanus*' enthesal pattern to shift more toward the great apes; however, among the australopiths, *A. africanus* shows the lowest FDS enthesal proportion, plotting outside the range of both *Pongo* and *Pan* (Fig. 12). Consequently, the apelike behavior constituting the mosaic enthesal pattern in *A. africanus* might not be related to finger flexion, and accordingly arboreal locomotion, but rather some other activity that we are not able to identify here. It is important to keep in mind that the *A. africanus* hand is a composite. Consequently, these conflicting signals may result from the fact that the bones of this hand belonged to different individuals. Unfortunately, due to the fragmented nature of the fossil record, it is currently not possible to address this matter.

Finally, the attachment sites of *A. afarensis* produced mixed results as well. However, in contrast to *A. africanus*, the different analyses appear to follow a more distinct trend. When the FDS is not included, *A. afarensis* presents an enthesal pattern on the margin of variation seen in later *Homo*, suggesting habitual humanlike hand use involving increased use of the fifth ray. Notably, the fifth digit of *A. afarensis* has been previously described as ape-like (Marzke et al., 1992). Its fifth metacarpal is less robust than in humans, where the robusticity of this bone is second only to the first metacarpal (Ricklan, 1987; Marzke et al., 1998). It has also been argued that the lack of a saddle joint between the hamate and the fifth metacarpal, which is a condition shared by all other australopiths, limits abduction and flexion in this joint and does not allow opposing the fifth finger against the thumb (Marzke, 1983; Domalain et al., 2017). As a consequence, *A. afarensis* has been deemed probably incapable of producing the Lomekwian tools as it was unable to “optimally orient the pulp of the 5th ray toward the hand-held object” (Domalain et al., 2017: 582) and therefore experienced limited grip force. This has been pointed out in particular by Domalain et al. (2017), who developed a sophisticated musculoskeletal model of *A. afarensis* to assess its ability to produce the Lomekwian stone tools. However, as the authors themselves cautioned, this model faces some limitations, among which are the inferred locations of muscle attachment sites. According to Domalain et al., muscle attachment sites are the anatomical parameter leading to the most significant difference in outcome in the *A. afarensis* model, yet the exact location of its attachment sites is assumed based on a human and a chimpanzee model scaled to bone dimensions, without being identified on the bone surfaces directly. Furthermore, it is worth emphasizing again the distinction between morphological evidence of habitual behavior versus biomechanical efficiency (see Karakostis, 2024). Even though a biomechanical model might reflect whether *A. afarensis* was efficient in producing the Lomekwian tools (i.e., whether its hand morphology would facilitate the tool production; e.g., Karakostis et al., 2021a), it cannot be used to infer its actual habitual behavior during life. In contrast, our analysis of habitual manual activity suggests that *A. afarensis* might have relied more on its fifth finger than previously suggested, regardless of how its dexterity may compare with other species. While our findings do not provide evidence that *A. afarensis* was the maker of the Lomekwian stone-tool industry, they indicate that it likely habitually engaged in humanlike hand use involving frequent power grasping and in-hand manipulation. Such behavior would likely be necessary for manipulating such large stone tools (Harmand et al., 2015).

Similar to *A. africanus*, including the FDS attachment site shifts the position of *A. afarensis* further towards great apes. Moreover, its FDS enthesal proportion is close to the mean and median of

P. troglodytes' and *P. pygmaeus*' FDS enthesal proportions, respectively (Fig. 12). A proportionately large FDS attachment site could potentially indicate that *A. afarensis* habitually engaged in arboreal locomotion. However, as discussed earlier, it is not possible to reconstruct a complex mode of locomotion based on the relative proportions of a single muscle. More research on the enthesal pattern of the upper limb would be required to help identify more definitive traces of habitual climbing in the *A. afarensis* skeleton.

In summary, the enthesal pattern of *A. afarensis* combines proportionately large attachment sites of muscles heavily involved in humanlike hand use with an apelike extrinsic finger flexor entheses. This mosaic pattern could suggest that *A. afarensis* engaged both in humanlike manipulation as well as apelike finger flexion, potentially in the context of arboreal locomotion. However, as with *A. africanus*, the *A. afarensis* bones used in our analyses belonged to different individuals. This limitation may have affected the results of our analyses as well.

4.3. Limitations

As is common in the analysis of the fossil record, our study faced some limitations. First, as stated earlier, the hand skeletons of *A. afarensis* and *A. africanus* are composites, meaning that they combine isolated bones that likely belonged to different individuals. This is problematic for activity reconstruction, as it might introduce conflicting signals (e.g., in case these individuals engaged in different lifetime activities). Unfortunately, to date, no complete hand skeletons have been recovered for these two species, leaving the composites as the only way to (cautiously) study their functional morphology.

Another limitation is the small number of entheses used in our analyses. Since preservation in the fossil record is generally poor, we limited the number of entheses to include as many individuals as possible. Moreover, as two of the three australopiths are represented by composite skeletons, including more bones means potentially introducing the habitual activity signals from even more individuals. Our overall choice of entheses was guided by ray involvement in humanlike manipulation (e.g., Napier, 1956; Marzke and Shackley, 1986; Marzke et al., 1992; Marzke, 1997; Marzke, 2013; Key et al., 2019), electromyographic research of muscle activation during humanlike tool use (Marzke et al., 1998; Key et al., 2020), and observations made in our previous VERA studies on hand and thumb use in humans and hominins (e.g., Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016; Karakostis et al., 2017; Kunze et al., 2022). Following this approach, we excluded muscles that have not been extensively analyzed. The majority of the entheses analyzed are located on the first ray due to the importance of the thumb in humanlike manipulation. Future studies should include more entheses located on different rays, preferably not from composite skeletons representing an unknown number of individuals. Further limitations to our choice of entheses are related to our sample composition. For example, the flexor pollicis longus and the extensor pollicis brevis are muscles that are highly relevant for humanlike manipulation but are absent in great apes and could therefore not be analyzed here (Diogo et al., 2012).

Related to the aforementioned, to keep the number of bones analyzed as small as possible (given the presence of composite hand skeletons for two of the three *Australopithecus* species of our sample; see Materials and Methods), we included the muscle origin site of D11 on the first metacarpal instead of analyzing its insertion site on the second proximal phalanx. However, it could be argued that the mechanical forces acting on the site of origin of a muscle might not be the same as on the insertion site, which could theoretically affect the results. Indeed, a previous VERA study on a medieval modern human sample did not find a direct bivariate

correlation between DI1's origin and insertion sites (Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016). Nevertheless, three previous experimental studies on laboratory animals showed that combining enthesal origin and insertion sites in a multivariate analysis can accurately elucidate activity-related differences across individuals (Karakostis et al., 2019a, 2019b; Karakostis and Wallace, 2023). Moreover, considering the exceptional importance of the DI1 muscle for humanlike manipulation (Marzke et al., 1998; Key et al., 2020), the observed trend of proportionally very large DI1 origin sites across the hominins of this study (as well as in Kunze et al., 2022) seems to be most parsimoniously explained by interspecies differences in habitual muscle use. Based on the aforementioned, perhaps the lack of a direct origin–insertion correlation in the medieval modern human sample (Karakostis and Lorenzo, 2016) may be due to the smaller activity differences expected within a single population sample of a species (as opposed to comparisons across distinct species with vastly different behaviors); perhaps such slighter manual activity differences may be more influential on the insertion site of a muscle (which experiences movement during muscle contraction; e.g., Jones and Lederman, 2006). Further extensive methodological research on DI1 is required to fully explore this possibility, preferably involving biomechanical modeling and/or individuals with documented activities.

Finally, it should be mentioned that our enthesis selection includes attachment sites of both intrinsic and extrinsic muscles. We generally would not expect the difference in muscle size between intrinsic and extrinsic muscles to affect our enthesal patterns as VERA aims to reconstruct the intraindividual distribution of mechanical strain across different muscle entheses of each individual, rather than to investigate differences in the size of muscles. Additionally, our previous studies on extensively documented human skeletons found clear activity-related differences based on multivariate enthesal analyses that combined intrinsic and extrinsic muscles together (Karakostis et al., 2017; Karakostis and Hotz, 2024). Nonetheless, the exact correlation between muscle size and bony enthesal surface is not entirely understood (e.g., see Hamrick et al., 2000; Montgomery et al., 2005; Williams-Hatala et al., 2016), and further methodological research is needed in the future to fully clarify if analyzing extrinsic and intrinsic muscle separately may be useful for activity reconstructions.

A result of the generally limited selection of muscle entheses is that we do not cover all possible grasping patterns, which could theoretically have provided more insights into manipulatory differences among species (e.g., across non-human great apes). However, we believe that the nature of the selection still allowed us to specifically address whether australopiths presented signs of humanlike hand use (which was clearly reflected in the human enthesal patterns of our analyses). Additionally, as we mentioned previously in the Discussion, our enthesis choice is also not necessarily suited—or intended—for a detailed investigation of arboreal locomotion or apelike manipulation in general. The reason for the latter is partly the lack of comprehensive knowledge about muscle activation patterns during great ape hand use (Bardo et al., 2017), which makes it difficult to determine which entheses might provide meaningful insight. Additionally, many muscles that are relevant for arboreal locomotion are located on the upper limb and not just the hand (e.g., Larson and Stern, 1986; Larson, 2018; van Beesel et al., 2022). We recommend that future studies expand the investigation of manipulative behavior in early hominins to even more entheses of the hand and upper limb. Moreover, our knowledge about great ape hand use would greatly benefit from investigations tailored to their behavior patterns (i.e., specifically investigating enthesal patterns in the upper limb of different ape species).

Finally, it should be noted that the anthropological methods currently proposed for reconstructing habitual activity based on skeletal remains (e.g., cross-sectional geometry or internal structure morphology) have not been tested using experimental designs that combine different species in the same study (and especially not primate species, which are more relevant for research on fossil hominins), possibly due to the various technical difficulties in developing such complex experimental models. This is also the case for VERA, whose capacity to identify activity-induced enthesal variation (when present) has been directly supported by four different experimental studies involving diverse animal species (Karakostis et al., 2019a, 2019b; Castro et al., 2022; Karakostis and Wallace, 2023). Consequently, most studies in our field explore hominin behavior through their comparison to extant primate species with known behavioral differences (e.g., Almécija et al., 2010; Dunmore et al., 2020a; Prang et al., 2021). In this comparative study, the distinctive enthesal patterns of late *Homo*, which were consistent with humanlike hand use (see Introduction), were absent in our great apes (as expected) but present in certain early hominins. We hereby propose that this similarity in enthesal morphology between humans and these early hominins is most parsimoniously explained by similarity in general manual behavior. Nevertheless, effects of genetic influence cannot be entirely excluded.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we investigated habitual hand use in *Australopithecus* based on a comparative analysis of their 3D enthesal patterns. Our results highlight the importance of the fifth finger for humanlike manipulation, as muscles attaching to this digit characterize habitual hand use in later *Homo*. Importantly, our study reports a high variability in reconstructed muscle activation patterns among australopiths. The enthesal proportions in *A. sediba* are more similar to those of later *Homo*, whereas *A. africanus* and *A. afarensis* present a mosaic enthesal pattern reflecting both humanlike and apelike hand use, to varying degrees. Additionally, the enthesal proportions of the extrinsic finger flexor tentatively suggest habitual arboreal locomotion in *A. sediba*, *A. afarensis*, and, to a lesser extent, *A. africanus*. However, more research focusing on the enthesal patterns of the entire upper limb is necessary for confirming such predictions on arboreality. Overall, our results suggest that *A. sediba* and *A. afarensis* habitually performed a suite of manual activities that were similar (yet not identical) to the power-squeeze grasping and in-hand manipulation patterns seen in later *Homo*. The frequent activation of muscles needed to perform characteristic humanlike grasping and manipulation in these early hominins lends support to the notion that humanlike hand use emerged prior to—and likely influenced—the evolutionary adaptations for higher manual dexterity in later hominins.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jana Kunze: Writing – review and editing, Writing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Verification. **Katerina Harvati:** Writing – review and editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Gerhard Hotz:** Writing – review and editing, Resources, Data curation. **Fotios Alexandros Karakostis:** Writing – review and editing, Writing, Methodology, Conceptualization, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary Online Material

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